

PERSONAL INNOVATIVENESS AND SKILL-BASED HABIT PERSPECTIVE IN SMARTPHONE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The emergence of new comers in smartphone industry has rapidly increased and has been looking to gain a place in global market. Accordingly, building customer loyalty has been perceived to be crucial to survive and success for the smartphone manufacturer. Previous researches have demonstrated that customer perceived value and customer habit are important predictor of customer loyalty. However, only few studies have investigated the moderating variables between these relationships. To fill this gap, this study therefore focuses on investigating the moderating role of personal innovativeness in the relationship between customer habit and repeat purchase intention. Habit construct in this study is focused on the skill developed in using the technology or also known as skill-based habit.

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1. Introduction

The emergence of mobile devices such as smartphone has not only changed the way the people communicate to each other, but also has changed the way the people deal with almost of their daily affairs. Moreover, with rapid development of mobile Apps and mobile websites, the use of smartphone nowadays has become more supportive in facilitating people to deal with daily activities, and has been considered to be the most important device in people's life.

According to Rainie and Perrin (2017), the number of smartphone users have been experiencing an increasing in both developed and developing countries [1]. For instance, the United States has been reported to have number of smartphone users increases from 97.87 million in 2011 to 224.3 million in 2017 which holds about 77% of its population [2]. Similarly, in Malaysia, the percentage of smartphone users has also been reported to increase from 68.7% in 2016 to 75.9% in 2017 of its population which comprising about 24.5 million smartphone users in 2017 [3].

The phenomenon of increasing the number of smartphone users have attracted the new comers to compete in the market. The emergence of new smartphone vendors into global market has made the competition in smartphone industry becomes fiercer than before. The leading smartphone brand such as Apple and Samsung showed a decline in sales by 5% and 3.6% respectively in 2017 [4]. On the other hand, the new comers of smartphone brand from China such as Huawei has been gradually gaining popularity in global market and has experience an increasing in sales by 7.6% in 2017 [4]. Another example is Xiaomi brand, another Chinese smartphone vendor which has been reported to double its market share from 3.3 % to 7.2 % in 2017 and it was ranked as number 4 in global market share [5]. With the increasing number of competitors in the market, customer loyalty thus becomes a top priority for smartphone vendors, therefore it is imperative that marketers can gain better understanding of the factors that influence customer loyalty in smartphone industry.

According to Valentine and Powers (2013), the best way to build customer loyalty is by focusing on the specific customer group or generation, as different customer generation has different characteristic thus requires different marketing strategy [6]. Accordingly, Generation Y has been regarded as the largest population as well as the most potential and beneficial customer among other generations particularly in mobile technology context such as smartphone [7]. The smartphone users in Malaysia are also mainly filled by the people who are in the age between 20-39 years old which also fall into Generation Y customers [8]. This Gen Y people hold about 57.8 % of smartphone users population in the country, followed by adults (40 – 49 years old) which holds 15.5% of population, seniors (above 50 years old) 14.5% of population, and preteens (below 20 years old) which holds 12.5% of population [8]. Studies have reported that Gen Y users have high purchasing power but they also have less loyalty level [9]. In an endeavor to foster the loyalty of Gen Y'ers in smartphone industry, it is therefore crucial for the smartphone manufacturers to comprehend the key drivers of customer loyalty.

Previous mobile technology related studies have suggested that customer perceived value is key determinant of customer loyalty [9,10]. The more value the customer received, the higher their intention to repurchase the product [11]. Although the concept of customer perceived value has been widely examined in smartphone context, however relatively few studies that have examined its effect on customer skill-based habit. Studies have argued that the continuance usage of smartphone may cause the users to develop specific skill in using smartphone which gradually may become a habit and may also affect their future purchase behavior [12].

Furthermore, as smartphone industry has constant innovations and continuously upgrades the existing devices and applications, the psychological factor related to innovativeness therefore need also to be considered when measuring customer loyalty [13]. As has been reported by Smith (2012) that Gen Y customers are likely to have capability to learn the technology faster than other generations [14], which indicates that their level of loyalty may also be influenced by their level of innovativeness towards the technology. In light of this, this study therefore aims to fill this gap by investigating the effect of perceived value on customer skill-based habit and the moderating effect of personal innovativeness on the relationship between customer skill-based habit and repurchase intention in the context of smartphone.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Repurchase intention

Although the concept of repurchase intention has been commonly applied in various fields of marketing literature particularly in Information System (IS) context such as blogging, e-learning, websites, online communities, mobile commerce, social networking websites, and self-service technology, however there are still lack of studies that focus on investigating customer repurchase intention in smartphone context [15]. In this study, customer repurchase intention can be defined as the customer strong commitment to purchase the same smartphone brand in the future. A number of IS related studies have noted that the concept of repurchase intention is the same concept with continuance intention, and does significantly predict the actual purchase of the product or technology [15].

Previous mobile technology related studies have been found to mostly focus on examining the effect of various value dimensions in measuring customer repurchase intention [15]. Despite perceived value has been considered as the core marketing strategy in retaining the customer [16], however it is also imperative to look at the drivers from non-value related factors in understanding customer decision to repurchase the same smartphone brand. The adoption of customer habit in measuring customer repurchase intention among the researchers in IS context

particularly in mobile technology has gained popularity in recent years. Studies have also proven that customer habit significantly influences customer intention to repurchase the same brand in the future [17]. Accordingly, besides customer perceived value, this study will also adopt customer habit construct to predict repurchase behavior of smartphone users.

2.2. Consumption value theory

Essentially, consumption value theory is used to predict customer behavioral choice. It was proposed by Sheth et al., (1991) who postulated that in consumption experience, the consumer will experience all or any of these five value dimensions such as functional value, emotional value, social value, epistemic value, and conditional value [18]. Functional value is defined as the customer perception about the utility acquired from product functionality or its physical performance. Social value is defined as the customer perception about the utility acquired from using the product related to the enhancement of social self-concept. Emotional value is defined as the customer perception of utility acquired related to the feeling arouse from using the product. Epistemic value is defined as the customer perception about the utility acquired related to novelty or curiosity from using the product. While conditional value is defined as the customer perception of utility acquired as a result of specific situation facing the choice maker. The key proposition of consumption value theory is that the value dimensions are independent to each other and make differential contributions to the behavioral choice incrementally.

Adopting the consumption value theory, the study of Sweeney and Soutar (2001) further has developed the scales and investigated the effect of four consumption values such as functional value, monetary value (subcomponent of functional value), emotional value, and social value on consumer choice in durable product category [19]. The study revealed that functional value, monetary value, emotional value, and social value significantly influence customer behavioral choice [19]. The study suggested that conditional value may have different order with other value dimensions as it is related to specific and transient set of circumstances [19]. While epistemic value has been urged to be considered in evaluating the product where innovations are important [19].

In consideration of the constant innovations and continuously upgrades the existing devices and applications in smartphone industry, this study therefore will adopt five value dimensions of perceived value in measuring repurchase intention including functional value, monetary value, emotional value, social value, and epistemic value.

2.3. Cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory

Customer habit has been gaining popularity in recent years in measuring customer behavioral intention particularly in IS context such as in microblog [17] and mobile applications [20]. Despite its popularity, the concept of habit has been mostly understood as the act of automaticity due to situational triggering factors which is also termed as usage habit or general habit. Apart from what has been commonly adopted in previous studies, the recent study is therefore aims to broaden the perspective of habit construct by focusing on the skill developed in using particular product or technology or also known as skill-based habit.

Cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory has been proposed by Murray and Haubl (2007) in further understanding on how habitual behavior in technology context is developed and may prevent people to switch to another technology [12]. Murray and Haubl (2007) has postulated that in repeated consumption experience of particular technology, people will develop specific skill in using that technology which gradually may become a habit (skill-based habit) [12]. As the skill that has been developed in incumbent technology is not transferrable to other technologies, thus it will create a switching cost due to the different ease of use between

incumbent technology and alternative technology, consequently it will lock-in the consumer from competitor and increase loyalty level.

In extending the cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory, the study of Polites and Karahanna (2012) has suggested that habit should be measured by three dimensions including awareness, controllability, and mental efficiency [21]. Controllability can be defined as the level of difficulty that the users perceived in controlling or resisting a particular behavior [21]. Awareness is defined as the extent to which the users may be unaware about the presenting of the situational cues that triggers them to do a particular behavior [21]. While mental efficiency can be referred as “the extent to which the perceptual or judgmental process demands attentional resources.” [21].

In line with the subsequent study of Polites and Karahanna (2012), the present study therefore adopts habit construct by focusing on the skill developed in using the technology or known as skill-based habit and conceptualize it as second order multidimensional construct that consist of three dimensions such as controllability, awareness, and mental efficiency.

2.4. *Personal innovativeness*

Personal innovativeness has been commonly adopted in technology related studies as technology often experience a constant change. Accordingly, the concept of personal innovativeness is mostly adopted to be the moderator between continuance intention and its predictor [22,13]. In the context of IS studies, personal innovativeness can be defined as the customer’s willingness to try out new information system or technology [23]. Studies have suggested adopting personal innovativeness variable is crucial in understanding customer purchase behavior particularly in mobile technology context [24].

The study of Jeong et al. (2017) has specifically focused on the effect of personal innovativeness on perceived innovation adoption factors (relative advantage, social image, aesthetics, and novelty) in the context of wearable devices [25]. The study has argued that customer innovativeness should be measured through two dimensions such as information-possessing innovativeness (IPI) and product-possessing innovativeness (PPI) in order to properly measure the nature and characteristics of personal innovativeness in IS context [25]. In line with the study of Jeong et al. (2017), the present study therefore adopts personal innovativeness as multidimensional construct that consist of PPI and IPI.

3. **Research model and hypothesis development**

The research model of this study is developed based on two underpinning theories which are customer perceived value theory [18] and cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory [12]. This study proposes that customer perceived value may have direct influence on customer skill-based habit. In addition, this study also argues that the effect of skill-based habit on repurchase intention may be moderated by personal innovativeness. The following hypotheses therefore are developed:

3.1. *Customer perceived value and repurchase intention relationship*

Customer perceived value has been regarded as the key strategy in all marketing activities [26]. Researches in IS related studies have also demonstrated that customer perceived value significantly influences customer purchase behavior in different fields of study such as social commerce [27], online retailing [11], online travel [28], and smartphone [29]. Previous study of Chen and Lin (2015) further has also found that the conceptualization of perceived value as second order reflective construct (e.g. functional value, emotional value, social value, epistemic value, and conditional value) significantly influences the continuance intention in IS context [30]. As perceived value associates with the benefits that the customer get from using the

product, thus it can be asserted that the more value the customer received, the higher their commitment to repurchase the product. The following hypothesis therefore is proposed:

H1: customer perceived value is positively correlated with repurchase intention

3.2. *Customer perceived value and customer skill-based habit relationship*

Previous studies have demonstrated that perceived value is positively correlated with customer habit [31,32,33]. The study of Chiu et al. (2012) further has argued that perceived value is antecedence of customer habit [34]. As smartphone provides users with various functions and features, it can be understood that the positive values or rewards gained from using smartphone will increase the use of smartphone itself thus will reinforce the habit formation [35]. Derived from cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory [12], the repeated experience in using particular technology will also make the users becoming more skilled in which it will become automatic as well. Accordingly, it can be inferred that the positive values gained from using smartphone will increase its usage which in return will also gradually develop skill-based habit. The following hypothesis therefore is proposed:

H2: customer perceived value is positively correlated with skill-based habit

3.3. *Customer skill-based habit and repurchase intention relationship*

In IS context, habit has been adopted to predict consumer continuance intention in different fields of study such as social media [31], mobile application [20], and Mobile financial services [36]. The relationship between habit and repeat purchase intention has also specifically investigated by previous studies within different IS context. For example, the study of Chiu et al., (2012) has investigated the moderating role of habit between trust and repeat purchase in online shopping context [34]. The study Hsu et al. (2015) further has added that habit plays moderating role in the relationship between repeat purchase intention and its predictors such as value, satisfaction, and trust in online shopping context [37]. While the study of Zhang et al. (2015) has evidenced that habit directly influence consumer loyalty (e.g. repeat purchase and word-of-mouth) in microblog context [17].

Although the role of habit has been investigated by previous IS related studies, however only few studies investigating the effect of habit on repurchase intention in smartphone context. In addition, the view of habit from skill-based perspective has not been investigated before either in IS context in general or in smartphone context in particular. Derived from the cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory [12], the consumer who has developed skill-based habit in using particular technology will likely to lock-in to that technology as it is not transferrable to another technologies, thus it will increase their loyalty level. Accordingly, it can be hypothesized that:

H3: customer skill-based habit has positive correlation with repeat purchase intention.

3.4. *Moderating role of personal innovativeness on skill-based habit and repeat purchase relationship*

Despite personal innovativeness has been considered to be crucial in explaining the adoption of new product or technology, however recent IS related study has also discovered that personal innovativeness has significant influence on post purchase behavior [22]. The study of Park et al. (2013) has found that personal innovativeness positively affects continuance intention in smartphone context [24]. While the study of Jianlin and Qi (2010) has evidenced that personal innovativeness significantly moderates the relationship between customer loyalty and its predictors such as customer satisfaction and switching cost in online shopping context [13]. It has been suggested that the customers with high level of innovativeness are likely to be risk

taking as they are willing to seek knowledge and to learn about the new technology, thus they are more possible to switch to another brand even with high loyalty level [13].

According to cognitive lock-in (skill-based habit) theory, the customers who have developed skill-based habit are likely to be loyal to their product or technology as their skill is not transferable to another technology [12]. However, in this regard, the study of Kroenung et al. (2017) has further found that the customers who have developed skill-based habit are likely to have less tendency to switch to another technology when they do not have favorable attitude towards another technology [38]. This finding indicates that there may be possibility of the customers who have developed skill-based habit to switch to another brand with respect to their innovativeness level. As has been argued by Wells et al. (2010) that customer with high innovativeness are likely to adopt the new technology when they perceived that the new technology to be better than incumbent technology, even though the new technology is perceived to be technologically complex and unfamiliar [39]. Accordingly, it can be hypothesized that:

H4: Personal innovativeness moderates the relationship between customer skill-based habit and repurchase intention.

Figure 1. Proposed Research Model

4. Research Method

This study focuses on the context of smartphone users in Malaysia since it is well-known that the country has been reported to have high market penetration in Asia [3]. Furthermore, it has been reported that Malaysian smartphone users have high dependency on smartphone usage [3], which indicates that the people in Malaysia use their smartphone frequently thus their skill-based habit in using smartphone may be well-developed. The respondent of this study will be focused on Generation Y smartphone users who are born between 1981 – 1997 or who are in the age between 21 – 37 years old in 2018 [40]. This is because not only Gen Y people are the largest smartphone users in Malaysia [3], but they also have been found to have high purchasing power and less loyalty [9].

The measurement scales used in this study are adopted and adapted from previous related studies. For perceived value variable, this study conceptualizes it as second order reflective construct as suggested by consumption value theory [18] and its measurements are adopted and adapted from the subsequence study of Sweeney and Soutar (2001) (for functional value, monetary value, emotional value, and social value) [19], and the study of Pihlström and Brush (2008) (for epistemic value) [41]. For skill-based habit variable, this study conceptualizes it as second order reflective construct as suggested by Bargh (1989) [42] and its measurement are adopted and adapted from the study of Polites and Karahanna (2012) [21]. For repurchase intention variable, the measurements are adopted from previous smartphone related study of Kim et al. (2016) [10]. And for personal innovativeness variable, this study conceptualizes it as multidimensional construct that consists of two dimensions (IPI and PPI) as suggested by the study of Jeong et al. (2017) [25] and its measurements are adopted and adapted from the study of Jeong et al. (2017) [25].

The total of 400 respondents will be required for this study and purposive sampling technique will be used via online survey. Prior data collection, the questionnaire pretesting which involves three academicians from related fields and two experts from related industry will be conducted to ensure its content validity. This study will use partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) for data analysis.

5. Conclusion

The objective of this study is to explore the factors influencing customer repurchase intention among Gen Y customers in smartphone industry. The personal trait factor such as personal innovativeness is included in the research model of this study to understand its moderating effect on the relationship between customer skill-based habit and repurchase intention. The finding of this study therefore is expected to provide useful information for both researchers and marketers in building customer loyalty in smartphone context.

References

- [1] Rainie L, Perrin A 2017 10 facts about smartphones as the iPhone turns 10. *Pew Res Cent*. Retrieved from: <http://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2017/06/28/10-facts-about-smartphones/>
- [2] <https://www.statista.com/statistics/201182/forecast-of-smartphone-users-in-the-us/>
- [3] Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission 2017 Hand phone users survey 2017. Malaysian Commun Multimed Comm. Retrieved from: <https://www.skmm.gov.my/skmmgovmy/media/General/pdf/HPUS2017.pdf>
- [4] <http://www.gartner.com>. 2018 Gartner Says Worldwide Sales of Smartphones Recorded First ver Decline During the Fourth Quarter of 2017. *Gartner*. Retrieved from: <https://www.gartner.com/newsroom/id/3859963>
- [5] <http://www.idc.com>. 2018 smartphone market chare vendor. *IDC*. Retrieved from: <https://www.idc.com/promo/smartphone-market-share/vendor>
- [6] Valentine DB, Powers TL 2013 Generation Y values and lifestyle segments. *J Consum Mark*. **30**(7), 597-606.
- [7] <http://www.nielsen.com>. 2016 Millennials Are Top Smartphone User. *Nielsen*. Retrieved from: <http://www.nielsen.com/us/en/insights/news/2016/millennials-are-top-smartphone-users.html>
- [8] Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission 2015 Hand phone users survey 2014. Malaysian Commun Multimed Comm. Retrieved from:

<https://www.mcmc.gov.my/skmmgovmy/media/General/pdf/MCMC-Hand-Phone-User19112015.pdf>

- [9] Chuah SHW, Marimuthu M, Kandampully J, Bilgihan A 2017 What drives Gen Y loyalty?
Understanding the mediated moderating roles of switching costs and alternative attractiveness in the value-satisfaction-loyalty chain. *J Retail Consum Serv.* **36**, 124-136.
- [10] Kim MK, Wong SF, Chang Y, Park JH. 2016 Determinants of customer loyalty in the Korean smartphone market: Moderating effects of usage characteristics. *Telemat Informatics.*
- [11] Chiu CM, Wang ETG, Fang YH, Huang HY. 2014 Understanding customers' repeat purchase intentions in B2C e-commerce: The roles of utilitarian value, hedonic value and perceived risk. *Inf Syst J.*
- [12] Murray KB, Häubl G. 2007 Explaining Cognitive Lock-In: The Role of Skill-Based Habits of Use in Consumer Choice. *J Consum Res.* **34**(1):77-88.
- [13] Jianlin W, Qi D. 2010 Moderating effect of personal innovativeness in the model for e-store loyalty. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on E-Business and E-Government, ICEE.*
- [14] Smith KT. 2012 Longitudinal study of digital marketing strategies targeting Millennials. *J Consum Mark.*
- [15] Filieri R, Lin Z. 2017 The role of aesthetic, cultural, utilitarian and branding factors in young Chinese consumers' repurchase intention of smartphone brands. *Comput Human Behav.*
- [16] Karjaluoto H, Jayawardhena C, Leppäniemi M, Pihlström M. 2012 How value and trust influence loyalty in wireless telecommunications industry. *Telecomm Policy.*
- [17] Zhang H, Zhang KZK, Lee MKO, Feng F. 2015 Brand loyalty in enterprise microblogs: Influence of community commitment, IT habit, and participation. *Inf Technol People.*
- [18] Sheth JN, Newman BI, Gross BL. 1991 Why we buy what we buy: A theory of consumption values. *J Bus Res.*
- [19] Sweeney JC, Soutar GN. 2001 Consumer perceived value: The development of a multiple item scale. *J Retail.*
- [20] Amoroso D, Lim R. 2017 The mediating effects of habit on continuance intention. *Int J Inf Manage.* **37**(6):693-702.
- [21] Polites GL, Karahanna E. 2012 Shackled to the Status Quo: The Inhibiting Effects of Incumbent System Habit, Switching Costs, and Inertia on New System Acceptance. *MIS Q.*
- [22] Huang TL, Liao S. 2015 model of acceptance of augmented-reality interactive technology:
the moderating role of cognitive innovativeness. *Electron Commer Res.*
- [23] Lu J. 2014 Are personal innovativeness and social influence critical to continue with mobile commerce? *Internet Res.*
- [24] Park N, Kim YC, Shon HY, Shim H. 2013 Factors influencing smartphone use and dependency in South Korea. *Comput Human Behav.*
- [25] Jeong SC, Kim SH, Park JY, Choi B. 2017 Domain-specific innovativeness and new product adoption: A case of wearable devices. *Telemat Informatics.*

- [26] Huber F, Herrmann A, Morgan RE. 2001 Gaining competitive advantage through customer value oriented management. *J Consum Mark.*
- [27] Hu X, Huang Q, Zhong X, Davison RM, Zhao D. 2016 The influence of peer characteristics and technical features of a social shopping website on a consumer's purchase intention. *Int J Inf Manage.*
- [28] Ponte EB, Carvajal-Trujillo E, Escobar-Rodríguez T. 2015 Influence of trust and perceived value on the intention to purchase travel online: Integrating the effects of assurance on trust antecedents. *Tour Manag.*
- [29] Wu S-I, Ho L-P. 2014 The Influence of Perceived Innovation and Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention of Innovation Product — An Example of iPhone. *Int J Innov Technol Manag.*
- [30] Chen SC, Lin CP. 2015 The impact of customer experience and perceived value on sustainable social relationship in blogs: An empirical study. *Technol Forecast Soc Change.*
- [31] Huang RT. 2018 What motivates people to continuously post selfies? The moderating role of perceived relative advantage. *Comput Human Behav.*
- [32] Yang S, Wang B, Lu Y. 2016 Exploring the dual outcomes of mobile social networking service enjoyment: The roles of social self-efficacy and habit. *Comput Human Behav.*
- [33] Kim B. 2012 The diffusion of mobile data services and applications: Exploring the role of habit and its antecedents. *Telecomm Policy.*
- [34] Chiu CM, Hsu MH, Lai H, Chang CM. 2012 Re-examining the influence of trust on online repeat purchase intention: The moderating role of habit and its antecedents. *Decis Support Syst.* **53**(4):835–45.
- [35] Limayem M, Hirt SG, Cheung CMK. 2007 How Habit Limits the Predictive Power of Intention: The Case of Information Systems Continuance. *MIS quarterly.*705-737.
- [36] Yen YS, Wu FS. 2016 Predicting the adoption of mobile financial services: The impacts of perceived mobility and personal habit. *Comput Human Behav.***65**:31–42.
- [37] Hsu MH, Chang CM, Chuang LW. 2015 Understanding the determinants of online repeat purchase intention and moderating role of habit: The case of online group-buying in Taiwan. *Int J Inf Manage.* **35**(1):45–56.
- [38] Kroenung J, Eckhardt A, Kuhlenkasper T. 2017 Conflicting behavioral paradigms and predicting IS adoption and non-adoption – The importance of group-based analysis. *Comput Human Behav.*
- [39] Wells JD, Campbell DE, Valacich JS, Featherman M. 2010 The Effect of Perceived Novelty on the Adoption of Information Technology Innovations: A Risk/Reward Perspective. *Decis Sci.*
- [40] Fry R. 2016 Millennials overtake Baby Boomers as America's largest generation. *Pew Res Cent.*
- [41] Pihlström M, Brush GJ. 2008 Comparing the perceived value of information and entertainment mobile services. *Psychol Mark.*

[42] Bargh JA. 1989 Conditional automaticity: Varieties of automatic influence in social perception and cognition. *Unintended thought*. **3** 51-69.

